

WorldFAIR WP08 URBAN HEALTH FIP01

Organization	GO FAIR
Created by	ANA ORTIGOZA (anitaortigoza2@gmail.com)
Based on	FIP Wizard 3, 0.0.1 (gofair:fip-wizard-3:0.0.1)
Project Phase	never
Project Tags	CODATA Type: FIP WorldFAIR
Created at	10 Oct 2022

I. About

Questions

No questions

II. Declare your FAIR Implementation Community

Questions

1

Select your FAIR Implementation Community

WorldFAIR WP08 URBAN HEALTH

This community derived from LAC-Urban Health Network. It is based on the work done at the SALURBAL project (Urban Health in Latin America) focused on collecting, harmonizing, and using data on the natural, built, and social environment as well as population health in 370 cities of 100,000 or more resident in 11 countries (Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, El Salvador, Guatemala, Mexico, Nicaragua, Panama, Peru)

<http://purl.org/np/RA6XF1wBIQtBN9sH-UVnma7fZVlo6CsOW8syt-NKZt30E#wf-wp08-urbanhealth>

2

Who is the Community Data Steward?

✓ Ana Ortigoza 0000-0001-8100-422X

3

Specify the start date for the validity of the FIP

✓ 2022-08-31

4

Specify the end date for the validity of the FIP

✓ 2024-05-31

III. Declarations for Findability

Questions

1

Declaration F1 Metadata: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of

any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5Xqbl2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- This is the best practice for many data related to social science (health and social urban environment)

2

Declaration F1 Data: What globally unique, persistent, resolvable identifier service do you use for datasets?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5Xqbl2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✓ ICPSR assigns to each variable- level identification that follows the DDI- XML markup

3

Declaration F2: What metadata schema do you use for findability?

- ✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DDI-Codebook|Data Documentation Initiative - Codebook

DDI-Codebook is a more light-weight version of the standard, intended primarily to document simple survey data. Originally DTD-based, DDI-C is also available as an XML Schema.

http://purl.org/np/RAh3tbu1Z7qqVD6Ool77Mp6Fjojk7scRTD_-l3ufWZpng#DDI-Codebook

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✓ DDI-XML are the codebook guidelines used by ICPSR ,

4

Declaration F3: What is the schema that links the persistent identifiers of your data to the metadata description?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

DOI | Digital Object Identifier

The digital object identifier (DOI) system originated in a joint initiative of three trade associations in the publishing industry (International Publishers Association; International Association of Scientific, Technical and Medical Publishers; Association of American Publishers). The system was announced at the Frankfurt Book Fair 1997. The International DOI Foundation (IDF) was created to develop and manage the DOI system, also in 1997. The DOI system was adopted as International Standard ISO 26324 in 2012. The DOI system implements the Handle System and adds a number of new features. The DOI system provides an infrastructure for persistent unique identification of objects of any type. The DOI system is designed to work over the Internet. A DOI name is permanently assigned to an object to provide a resolvable persistent network link to current information about that object, including where the object, or information about it, can be found on the Internet. While information about an object can change over time, its DOI name will not change. A DOI name can be resolved within the DOI system to values of one or more types of data relating to the object identified by that DOI name, such as a URL, an e-mail address, other identifiers and descriptive metadata. The DOI system enables the construction of automated services and transactions. Applications of the DOI system include but are not limited to managing information and documentation location and access; managing metadata; facilitating electronic transactions; persistent unique identification of any form of any data; and commercial and non-commercial transactions. The content of an object associated with a DOI name is described unambiguously by DOI metadata, based on a structured extensible data model that enables the object to be associated with metadata of

any desired degree of precision and granularity to support description and services. The data model supports interoperability between DOI applications. The scope of the DOI system is not defined by reference to the type of content (format, etc.) of the referent, but by reference to the functionalities it provides and the context of use. The DOI system provides, within networks of DOI applications, for unique identification, persistence, resolution, metadata and semantic interoperability.

http://purl.org/np/RAnAWGdel_1GGmDAqv-vZjby5Xqbl2ZujNz1vgwK_6cRI#DOI

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

5

Declaration F4 Metadata: Which service do you use to publish your metadata records?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Inter University Consortium for Political and Social Research

An international consortium of more than 750 academic institutions and research organizations, Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) provides leadership and training in data access, curation, and methods of analysis for the social science research community.

<http://purl.org/np/RAvSKSoRBICN4W97XU4QHODnJPjIP8VlrGhmqy5-RZbq8#ICPSR>

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- DOI identifier through ICPSR

6

Declaration F4 Datasets: Which service do you use to publish your datasets?

- b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

6.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

6.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Inter University Consortium for Political and Social Research

An international consortium of more than 750 academic institutions and research organizations, Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) provides leadership and training in data access, curation, and methods of analysis for the social science research community.

<http://purl.org/np/RAvSKSoRBICN4W97XU4QHODnJPjIP8VlrGhmqy5-RZbq8#ICPSR>

6.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

6.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- This question has not been answered yet!*

IV. Declarations for Accessibility

Questions

1

Declaration A1.1 Metadata: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DDI-Codebook

DDI Codebook is a more light-weight version of the standard, intended primarily to document simple survey data. Originally DTD based. DDI C is also available as an XML Schema.

http://purl.org/np/RAR_N3FXez3hzFxLSTvwrZJTvRyNrPICOI3Zzgg34hy6s#DDI-C

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

2

Declaration A1.1 Datasets: Which standardized communication protocol do you use for datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DDI-Codebook

DDI Codebook is a more light-weight version of the standard, intended primarily to document simple survey data. Originally DTD based. DDI C is also available as an XML Schema.

http://purl.org/np/RAR_N3FXez3hzFxlSTvwrZJTvRyNrPICOI3Zzqq34hy6s#DDI-C

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

3

Declaration A1.2 Metadata: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

Inter University Consortium for Political and Social Research

An international consortium of more than 750 academic institutions and research organizations, Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) provides leadership and training in data access, curation, and methods of analysis for the social science research community.

<http://purl.org/np/RAvSKSoRBICN4W97XU4QHODnJPjIP8VlrGhmgy5-RZbq8#ICPSR>

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

4

Declaration A1.2 Datasets: Which authentication & authorisation service do you use for datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

Inter University Consortium for Political and Social Research

An international consortium of more than 750 academic institutions and research organizations, Inter-university Consortium for Political and Social Research (ICPSR) provides leadership and training in data access, curation, and methods of analysis for the social science research community.

<http://purl.org/np/RAvSKSoRBICN4W97XU4QHODnJPjIP8VlrGhmgy5-RZbq8#ICPSR>

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

5

Declaration A2: What metadata preservation policy do you use?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

5.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

5.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

RDA CTS | RDA Core Trust Seal Certification

The RDA Repository Audit and Certification DSA-WDS Partnership Working Group (WG) produced a two-part recommendation, one of which includes a Catalogue of Common Procedures for certification. The goal of the effort was to create a set of harmonized Common Procedures for certification of repositories at the basic level, drawing from the procedures already put in place by the Data Seal of Approval (DSA) and the ICSU World Data System (ICSU-WDS). These procedures are intended to support the implementation of the Catalogue of Common Requirements developed by the WG to harmonize the certification criteria previously established by the DSA and ICSU-WDS.

http://purl.org/np/RA6lJGt5TRNo9XpCM5XcNKlhEDIGWTVZ6iUyhff0bfwX4#RDA_CTS

5.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

5.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

V. Declarations for Interoperability

Questions

1

Declaration I1 Metadata: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

XMLS | eXtensible Markup Language Schema

XMLS defines and describes a class of XML documents by using schema components to constrain and document the meaning, usage and relationships of their constituent parts: datatypes, elements and their content and attributes and their values.

http://purl.org/np/RA5E0NA_BAilxwHhZKQm-ltnFoxw3atel8UFxZ0rs8N5Q#XML_Schema

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

2

Declaration I1 Datasets: What knowledge representation language (allowing machine interoperation) do you use for datasets?

✔ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✔

XMLS | eXtensible Markup Language Schema

XMLS defines and describes a class of XML documents by using schema components to constrain and document the meaning, usage and relationships of their constituent parts: datatypes, elements and their content and attributes and their values.

http://purl.org/np/RA5E0NA_BAilxwHhZKQm-ltnFoxw3atel8UFxZ0rs8N5Q#XML_Schema

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✔ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3

Declaration I2 Metadata: What structured vocabulary do you use to annotate your metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ICD10|International Classification of Diseases Version 10

The ICD is the international standard diagnostic classification for all general epidemiological, many health management purposes and clinical use. ICD-10 is the 10th revision of the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Related Health Problems (ICD), a medical classification list by the World Health Organization (WHO). It contains codes for diseases, signs and symptoms, abnormal findings, complaints, social circumstances, and external causes of injury or diseases.

http://purl.org/np/RA24i_JSjDvLrfGD8WYPzyFBYVWBQm3DXmVXVezZUaCk#ICD-10

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.b.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

ISO 3166-1:2013 Codes for the representation of names of countries and their subdivisions - Part 1: Country codes

ISO 3166-1:2013 is intended for use in any application requiring the expression of current country names in coded form. It also includes basic guidelines for its implementation and maintenance.

http://purl.org/np/RAKy68K-ubbaV8BKrbYyJQ1NYKcCkvQPpgrQ7rdWbvjRU#ISO_3166

3.b.1.b.2

This implementation choice is:

- ✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.b.3

Implementation Consideration

- ✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

3.b.1.c.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

American Standard Code for Information Interchange

The American Standard Code for Information Interchange (ASCII) is a standard table of seven-bit designations for digital representation of uppercase and lowercase Roman letters, numbers and special control characters in teletype, computer and word processor systems.

http://purl.org/np/RAG4lvGYEn3Q0b1FGZW9y4Ccf_FjUGexwnPZwt3YTjXyc#ASCII

3.b.1.c.2

This implementation choice is:

a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.c.3

Implementation Consideration

This question has not been answered yet!

4

Declaration I2 Datasets: What structured vocabulary do you use to encode your datasets

b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

American Standard Code for Information Interchange

The American Standard Code for Information Interchange (ASCII) is a standard table of seven-bit designations for digital representation of uppercase and lowercase Roman letters, numbers and special control characters in teletype, computer and word processor systems.

http://purl.org/np/RAG4lvGYEn3Q0b1FGZW9y4Ccf_FjUGexwnPZwt3YTjXyc#ASCII

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

- a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

This question has not been answered yet!

5

Declaration I3 Metadata: What semantic model do you use for your metadata records?

- a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

6

Declaration I3 Datasets: What semantic model do you use for your datasets?

✓ a. Declaration: No implementation choice has been made by this community

VI. Declarations for Reusability

Questions

1

Declaration R1.1 Metadata: Which usage license do you use for your metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

1.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

1.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

CC BY 4.0 | Attribution 4.0 International

Using this licence you are free to share and adapt the resource but you must give appropriate credit.

http://purl.org/np/RAQ_sGdY_Qc7l1O_zmn4nr-pMBOxKU04Ur9s998rS6Fc#CC-BY-4.0

1.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

1.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

2

Declaration R1.1 Datasets: Which usage license do you use for your datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

2.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

2.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

CC BY 4.0 | Attribution 4.0 International

Using this licence you are free to share and adapt the resource but you must give appropriate credit.

http://purl.org/np/RAQ_sGdY_Qc7l1O_zmn4nr-pMBOxKU04Ur9s998rS6Fc#CC-BY-4.0

2.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

2.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ This question has not been answered yet!

3

Declaration R1.2 Metadata: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your metadata records?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

3.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

3.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

DDI-Codebook|Data Documentation Initiative - Codebook

DDI-Codebook is a more light-weight version of the standard, intended primarily to document simple survey data. Originally DTD-based, DDI-C is also available as an XML Schema.

http://purl.org/np/RAh3tbu1Z7qqVD6Ool77Mp6Fjojk7scRTD_-l3ufWZpng#DDI-Codebook

3.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

3.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✗ *This question has not been answered yet!*

4

Declaration R1.2 Datasets: What metadata schema do you use for describing the provenance of your datasets?

✓ b. Declaration: FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

4.b.1

List the FAIR Enabling Resource(s)

Answers

4.b.1.a.1

Select the FAIR Enabling Resource

✓

DDI-Codebook|Data Documentation Initiative - Codebook

DDI-Codebook is a more light-weight version of the standard, intended primarily to document simple survey data. Originally DTD-based, DDI-C is also available as an XML Schema.

http://purl.org/np/RAh3tbu1Z7qqVD6Ool77Mp6Fjojk7scRTD_-l3ufWZpng#DDI-Codebook

4.b.1.a.2

This implementation choice is:

✓ a. Currently in use by the community

4.b.1.a.3

Implementation Consideration

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

5

Declaration R1.3: Your community uses this FAIR Implementation Profile to link to domain-relevant community standards.

✘ *This question has not been answered yet!*

VII. Register a new resource as a nanopublication

Questions

No questions